

METABOLISM OF NEUROMEDIATORY AMINO ACIDS IN DIFFERENT BRAIN DIVISIONS**Omar Parvin Mirdamat***Sumgayit State University, Sumgayit, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

The morpho-functional differentiation and maturation of different departments of the brain are accompanied by changes in the amount of number of biologically active substances, amino acids, proteins, and lipids. When studying the protein metabolism occurring in nerve tissue, it was determined that this tissue contains many substituted and non-substituted amino acids and enzymes involved in amino acid metabolism. These indicate that amino acid metabolism and protein biosynthesis occur with particular intensity in nervous tissue.

Keywords: amino acid, lipid, postnatal, cytomorphological, electrophysiological, GABA-gamma aminobutyric acid

Introduction

Studying the activity of the central nervous system is one of the most demanding and particularly important issues facing the science of neurophysiology. The central nervous system creates interaction between the cells, tissues and individual parts of the body, ensuring their completeness. It also regulates the processes in the body and keeps all its activities under control by directing the work of the organs. It depends on the functional state of the CNS in the relationship between the organism and the external environment [1].

Among the functional structures of the central nervous system, the cerebral cortex is the body's cardiovascular system, respiratory system, muscle tone, and metabolism, etc. combines complex biological functions related to Cerebral cortex departments, as well as the coordination of movement, homeostasis protection, integrate the primary learning centres [4,7].

According to literature sources, shell derivatives and morpho-functional differentiation of the brain begin to form in the early stage of postnatal ontogenesis. In early postnatal ontogenesis, fundamental cytomorphological and electrophysiological changes take place in different departments of the brain [1,2].

It has been established that the functional maturation of separate structures of the brain and subcortical derivatives begins at different times.

As it was discovered, the functional maturity of brain structures of humans and different species of animals does not proceed with the same intensity in postnatal ontogeny.

In early postnatal ontogeny, the electrical activity of the brain of animals does not differ significantly for sleep and wakefulness. This is explained by the fact that the maturation of the functional maturity and structural organization of different departments of the brain corresponds to the state of the reticular system, ascending departments of the thalamus nucleus.

The variation in the speed of emergence of action forms of conditioned reflex reactions and the localization of action forms corresponds to the later stages of postnatal ontogenesis. Therefore, compared to general motor acts, the performance of local responses is one of the most complex issues of postnatal ontogenesis for the animal's central nervous system [3,4].

It is known from literary sources that the level of functional development in the cerebral cortex and subcortical structure is determined in the process of ontogenesis. It is observed in the morphological improvements in the brain. The maturation of the central nervous system in corresponding stages and the determination of its electrical activity stabilizes at the end of the first month of life in animals belonging to relatively low levels of phylogenetic development. Functional formation in the cortical structures of the brain of hares ends in the 3rd and 4th months.

The development of the brain refers to the period from the neonatal stage to the period of sexual maturity [5,7]. According to the morphological, electrophysiological, biochemical and compositional indicators obtained by reflective methods, the functional and morphological maturity of the brain in postnatal ontogeny can be classified as follows.

The first stage covers the first two stages of life. At this time, the mass of the brain increases intensively. The second stage covers the period up to the 45th day of life, and at this time, although the intensity of the increase in the mass of the brain decreases, the process stops completely. In the third stage, the growth of its mass up to three months of age is practically stopped.

In mammals, CNS indicators are characterized by the development of the neocortex. Its cytoarchitectonics (associative, projection zones, etc.) are used in the process of development of the cerebral cortex in phylogeny and ontogeny in increasing the differentiation of neuron organizations: in the formation of neurons of different shapes, in the increase of their quantity, in the change of synaptic contact types, in the development of protrusions, etc.

Neurons in the cerebral cortex differ according to their distribution opposition, their shape and structure, and their size, as well as the functional relevance of biochemical processes.

The morphological characteristics of pyramidal neurons include their large size, multi-branching of dendrites, an abundance of communication with other cells, large mass and distance of the axon from the body of the neuron.

On the 10th-12th days of postnatal ontogenesis, the amount of mature pyramidal neurons increases, the volume of the cytoplasm increases, and the growth of

basal dendrites is strong in its apical part. At this time, a new qualitative form of synaptic contact is created.

In newborns, the conditioned reflex is weak. This is due to the diversity of maturation of the brain and different departments of the cerebral cortex.

The development of excitation and inhibition of the main processes in the cerebral cortex determines the provision of conditioned reflex activity. The highest level of cortical processes is manifested in island rabbits at 35-45 days.

As a result of a series of neuro-histological studies, neurons were classified according to their shape, size, and degree of branching of axons and dendrites. Morpho-functional correction of neurons and the diversity of internal structures of synaptic neurons were revealed through the electron microscope.

Recently, special attention has been paid to the study of the sensitivity of immature neurons to mediators and their functional nature in different periods of postnatal ontogenesis. As a result of studying the electrophysiological indicators of neurons in the embryo and early postnatal ontogenesis, it was revealed that there is an interaction between the structure of the developing neuron and its function. Quality was observed on the basis of morphological changes according to electrophysiological phenomenon indicators.

It was determined by the conducted research that the morpho-functional differentiation and maturation of various departments of the brain are accompanied by changes in the amount of a number of biologically active substances, amino acids, proteins, and lipids. This idea was confirmed by a number of parallel biochemical studies [4,5,6].

There is a high pool of proteins and amino acids in the brain. Amino acids and proteins occupy a central position in nitrogen metabolism.

When studying the protein metabolism occurring in nerve tissue, it was determined that this tissue contains many substituted and non-substituted amino acids and enzymes involved in amino acid metabolism. These indicate that amino acid metabolism and protein biosynthesis occur with extraordinary intensity in nervous tissue.

Glutamic acid has a special role in the metabolism of the brain. Ammonia generated in nerve tissue is mainly neutralized by combining with glutamic acid. Glutamic acid combines with ammonia and turns into glutamine, which is harmless to nerve tissue. So, while glutamine easily passes from the blood to the cerebrospinal fluid, glutamic acid can cross the blood-brain barrier with great difficulty. It is hypothesized that glutamic acid is aminated to pass from the blood to the nerve tissue. must be converted to glutamine. Glutamic acid can also be produced synthetically in nervous tissue. Part of the ammonia produced in the brain is used for the synthesis of glutamic acid. QABA, which is an exchange product of glutamic acid, occupies an important place in the metabolism of neurons. Glutamic acid in nerve tissue is sharply separated from other

amino acids due to its quantity and participation in metabolic processes. Among its exchange products, glutamine, metaglutarate, and gamma-amino fatty acid occupy a critical place in the metabolism of neurons. In nerve tissue, glutamic acid is sharply separated from other amino acids by its quantity and participation in metabolic processes. Of its exchange products, glutamine, metaglutarate and gamma-amino fatty acid are particularly active substances. Together, they make up more than half of the brain's amino acid pool. The metabolism of glutamic acid consists of a series of complex reactions catalyzed by specific enzymes. The glutamate dehydrogenase enzyme, which is specific for brain tissue, is involved in the synthesis of glutamic acid but is also very sensitive to the increase of ammonia in the brain. When excess ammonia accumulates in the brain, the glutamate dehydrogenase enzyme uses most of it in the conversion reaction of glutamic acid. Glutaminetase enzyme is also involved in this process.

It is known that gamma-amino-fatty acid plays an important role in the exchange processes in the brain tissue. Although glutamine is not oxidized in the brain tissue, it is less useful for the energy supply of the brain and acts as a donor of amino groups for the synthesis of substituted amino acids. RETURN is particularly characteristic of the brain. It is formed as a result of the separation of a carboxyl group from glutamic acid.

The determination of the physiological role of QABA as an inhibitory mediator, its participation in bioenergetic processes, and the significance of the intracellular position in the permeability of the cell membrane in complex metabolic processes are significant for the cytochemical studies carried out consistently.

References

1. Сәғәров Ф.И. İnsan fiziologiyası. Bakı: Təbib, 1997, s. 383,430
2. Авшарская Э.И. Нейрогуморальные механизмы регуляции кровообращения в онтогенезе. В кн. Вопросы физиологии и патологии ЛНС человека животных в онтогенезе. М.: 1981, с. 131-138
3. Аверинова Е.А. Богданова Е.В.Сытинский И.А., Толкачев Г.Н Изменение активности ферментов обмена гамма-аминомасляной кислоты мозгы крыс в онтогенезе.М.: 1965,т.2, с 493-498.
4. Okusky J.R. and McGeber E.G. Methylmercury Poisoning the Developing nervous system in the rat. 1985,v. 21 № 2, pp. 299-306.
5. Tapia R., Meza-Ruiz G. Differences in some properties of newborn and adult brain glutamate decarboxylase .J.1975, v.6, pp.171-181.
6. VerlingL.L.,al., (--H) Glutamatebinding to hippocampal synaptic membranes. J. of J. Neurochemistry, raven Press, New York, 1983, pp 586-593.
7. Dravid A.R., Himvich V.A., Davis J.M. Some free amino acids in dig brain during development. J.neurochem, 1965, v.12,pp. 901-906.